

Integration of Qualitative and Quantitative Methods for Environmental Management: Case Study in the Plastics Processing Industry

Integração de Métodos Qualitativos e Quantitativos para a Gestão Ambiental: Estudo de Caso na Indústria de Transformados Plásticos
Integración de métodos cualitativos y cuantitativos para la gestión ambiental: un estudio de caso en la industria de los plásticos procesados

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Abstract: This study presented an innovative model for identifying and prioritizing stakeholders in the environmental performance of a plastics processing industry using a mixed methods approach. The research was divided into two phases: qualitative and quantitative. In the qualitative phase, action research and focus groups were conducted to identify stakeholders and their needs. In contrast, the quantitative phase used the *Analytic Hierarchy Process* (AHP) method to prioritize stakeholders. The results highlighted the importance of the influence of government agencies. They suggested a model applicable to organizations in the plastics sector, aiming at the continuous improvement of their Environmental Management Systems (EMS). This work contributed significantly to the theory and practice of environmental management, offering a solid basis for innovative and effective solutions.

Keywords: ABNT NBR ISO 14001; Mixed methods; Environmental Management System; Stakeholders.

Resumo: Este estudo apresentou um modelo inovador para a identificação e hierarquização das partes interessadas no desempenho ambiental de uma indústria de transformação de material plástico, utilizando uma abordagem de métodos mistos. A pesquisa foi dividida em duas fases: qualitativa e quantitativa. Na fase qualitativa, foram realizadas pesquisas-ação e grupos focais para identificar as partes interessadas e suas necessidades, enquanto a fase quantitativa utilizou o método *Analytic Hierarchy Process* (AHP) para hierarquizar as partes interessadas. Os resultados destacaram a importância da influência dos órgãos governamentais e sugerem um modelo aplicável para organizações no setor de plásticos, visando a melhoria contínua de seus Sistemas de Gestão Ambiental (SGA). Este trabalho

contribuiu significativamente para a teoria e prática da gestão ambiental, oferecendo uma base sólida para soluções inovadoras e eficazes.

Palavras-chave: ABNT NBR ISO 14001; Métodos mistos; Sistema de Gestão Ambiental; Stakeholders.

Resumen: Este estudio presentó un modelo innovador para la identificación y priorización de las partes interesadas en el desempeño ambiental de una industria de procesamiento de plástico, utilizando un enfoque de métodos mixtos. La investigación se dividió en dos fases: cualitativa y cuantitativa. En la fase cualitativa, se llevó a cabo una investigación-acción y grupos focales para identificar a los interesados y sus necesidades, mientras que en la fase cuantitativa se utilizó el método del Proceso de Jerarquía Analítica (AHP) para clasificar a los interesados. Los resultados destacaron la importancia de la influencia de las agencias gubernamentales y sugieren un modelo aplicable para las organizaciones del sector del plástico, con el objetivo de la mejora continua de sus Sistemas de Gestión Ambiental (SGA). Este trabajo ha contribuido significativamente a la teoría y la práctica de la gestión ambiental, ofreciendo una base sólida para soluciones innovadoras y efectivas.

Palabras clave: ISO 14001; Métodos Mixtos; Sistema de Gestión Ambiental; Grupos de interés.

1 INTRODUCTION

Environmental management is a growing concern in the global context, especially with the need for practices that support the circular economy and industrial sustainability. The ISO 14001:2015 standard was developed to meet these needs, providing a standard Environmental Management System (EMS) that improves internal control and promotes the reduction of environmental impacts. This study proposes a model for identifying and prioritizing stakeholders in organizations' environmental performance, contributing to effective environmental management.

In a global scenario where the demand for a higher standard of living drives a constant growth in the consumption of products and services, careful management of resource use and minimization of pollutant emissions have become essential. Awareness of the effects of human consumption on the environment, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and risks to human health, has motivated consumers, legislators, and corporations to reconsider their practices (Rosa, Guesser, Hein, Pfitscher, & Lunkes, 2015).

In this context, consumers look for options that reflect environmental responsibility. At the same time, legislators strive to formulate laws promoting sustainable production and consumption practices, facing global environmental conservation challenges (Carvalho, Mimoso, Mendes, & Matos, 2014).

The last three decades have been marked by progress in adopting environmental standards. Through private and nongovernmental regulations, corporations have committed to improving their environmental management practices. Among these initiatives, the ISO 14001 standard stands out, developed by the *International Organization for Standardization* (ISO), which established guidelines for environmental management systems (EMS), encouraging the continuous improvement of business practices in favor of the environment (Milazzo et al., 2017). This certification strengthened trust among stakeholders and aligned productivity and profitability with environmental commitment, following the standards established by the ISO 14000 family (Milazzo et al., 2017).

First introduced in 1996, the ISO 14001 standard proposes an EMS model that can be implemented by any organization, regardless of its size, culture, or location. It emphasizes the importance of adopting practices that respect corporate environmental responsibilities (Pryshlakivsky & Searcy, 2013; Tien, Chung, & Tsai, 2002). This system has become one of the most widely adopted globally for managing environmental aspects and impacts in companies (Oliveira et al., 2016).

The importance of stakeholders was highlighted shortly after introducing ISO 14001. Studies indicate that corporations with more outstanding environmental commitment tend to actively involve diverse groups in their practices, unlike those with less commitment (Henriques & Sadorski, 1999). According to the Brazilian Association of Technical Standards (ABNT, 2015a), the 2015 revision of

the standard emphasized the need for organizations to understand and meet stakeholder expectations, whether mandatory or voluntary.

The ISO 14001:2015 version was developed in response to market needs for practices that support the circular economy and industrial sustainability (Milazzo et al., 2017). A standardized EMS not only improves internal control but also promotes the reduction of environmental impacts, mainly when supported by adequate public policies (Alonso-Pauli & André, 2015).

Thus, the following research question emerges: How can integrating Qualitative and Quantitative Methods transform Environmental Management in the plastics industry?

This study proposed a model for identifying and prioritizing stakeholders in organizations' environmental performance, contributing to effective environmental management. In addition to this introduction, the work is structured in five more sections, which include the theoretical basis, the characterization of the studied sector, the methodology, the results, and, finally, the final considerations and suggestions for future research.

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The updated version of the ISO 14001 standard has brought several significant improvements, paving the way for superior environmental performance. Innovations include proactive actions for environmental improvement, deeper involvement of senior management, detailed product life cycle analysis, improved risk-based thinking, and more effective communication strategies. These changes raise the bar for environmental management and reinforce organizations' commitment to sustainability.

In the contemporary scenario, where environmental preservation has become a pressing issue and the debate on environmental management in organizations is gaining momentum, cutting-edge companies are increasingly engaged in adopting environmental management practices, recognizing that the transition to more sustainable operations involves a complex combination of human and operational factors essential for the "green transformation" of organizations (Jabbour et al., 2015).

Barbieri (2007) offered a comprehensive view by defining environmental management as a set of operational and administrative practices designed to generate positive impacts on the environment. These practices aim to prevent, reduce, or mitigate environmental damage resulting from human activities. Improving environmental performance, therefore, is understood as reducing a company's negative impacts on the environment, ranging from reducing emissions and waste to the conscious choice of raw materials and the efficient use of resources (Tien, Chung, & Tsai, 2002).

Organizations that view pollution not only as an unwanted byproduct of their operations but as a central aspect to be managed within their business model gain greater visibility and recognition. Environmental Management Systems

(EMS) certification has emerged as an effective strategy for companies to publicly demonstrate their commitment to sustainability and meet the growing demands of a more conscious market and consumers (Campos, 2012).

Alberton (2003) emphasized that implementing an EMS leads to reassessing the production process and driving the search for procedures and standards that minimize environmental damage. Compliance with the ABNT NBR ISO 14001 standard ensures that the organization meets legal requirements and considers significant environmental impacts when defining its policies and objectives (Campos, 2012).

As Weingarten, Pagell, and Fynes (2013) pointed out, the pursuit of ISO 14001 certification is motivated by the need for a strategic and comprehensive approach to corporate environmental policy, including its plans and actions. The ABNT NBR ISO 14001:2015 standard highlighted the role of the EMS in providing organizations with a robust framework for environmental protection that is adaptable to changing environmental conditions and aligned with socioeconomic needs (ABNT, 2015b).

The evolution of EMS approaches is illustrated by comparing the models proposed in the last two revisions of the ISO 14001 standard. This highlights the progress and adaptation of environmental management strategies to new realities and challenges. This panorama reinforces the growing importance of strategic environmental management in organizations, marking a promising path toward corporate sustainability and environmental preservation in the 21st century.

Figure 1 – Evolution of the concept of the scope of the environmental management system

Source: ABNT (2004, 2015a).

It is noted that the standard's objective, which in 2004 consisted of providing the organization with a structure for environmental protection, was expanded by including the social perspective through the terms "socioeconomic needs." Figure 2 explores the differences between the 2004 and 2015 revisions in more detail.

Figure 2 – Comparison between standards

Itens	2004	2015
Objetivo da norma	Prover as organizações de elementos de um sistema da gestão ambiental (SGA) eficaz que possam ser integrados a outros requisitos da gestão, e auxiliá-las a alcançar seus objetivos ambientais e econômicos.	Prover as organizações uma estrutura para a proteção do meio ambiente e possibilitar uma resposta às mudanças das condições ambientais em equilíbrio com as necessidades socioeconômicas.
Conceito PDCA aplicado ao SGA	Planejar: estabelecer os objetivos e processos necessários para atingir os resultados em concordância com a política ambiental da organização; Executar: implementar os processos; Verificar: monitorar e medir os processos em conformidade com a política ambiental, objetivos, metas, requisitos legais e outros, e relatar os resultados; Agir: agir para continuamente melhorar o desempenho dos sistema de gestão ambiental.	Planejar: estabelecer os objetivos ambientais e os processos necessários para entregar resultados de acordo com a política ambiental da organização; Executar: implementar os processos conforme planejado; Checar: monitorar e medir os processos em relação à política ambiental, incluindo seus compromissos, objetivos ambientais e critérios operacionais, e reportar os resultados; Agir: tomar ações para melhoria contínua.
Sistema de gestão	É um conjunto de elementos inter-relacionados utilizados para estabelecer a política e objetivos e para atingir esse objetivos. Inclui estrutura organizacional, atividade de planejamento, responsabilidade, práticas, procedimentos, processos e recursos.	É o conjunto de elementos inter-relacionados ou interativos de uma organização para estabelecer políticas, objetivos e processos para alcançar esses objetivos. Pode abordar uma única disciplina ou várias disciplinas (gestão da qualidade, gestão ambiental, gestão da saúde e segurança ocupacional, gestão da energia, gestão financeira etc.). Incluem a estrutura da organização, papéis e responsabilidades, planejamento e operação, avaliação de desempenho e melhoria. O escopo pode incluir a totalidade da organização, funções específicas e identificadas da organização, seções específicas e identificadas da organização, ou uma ou mais funções dentro de um grupo de organizações.
Sistema de gestão ambiental	Parte de um sistema da gestão de uma organização utilizada para desenvolver e implementar sua política ambiental e para gerenciar aspectos ambientais.	Parte do sistema de gestão usado para gerenciar aspectos ambientais, cumprir requisitos legais e outros requisitos, e abordar riscos e oportunidades.
Objetivo ambiental	Propósito ambiental geral, decorrente da política ambiental que uma organização se propõe a atingir.	Objetivo definido pela organização, coerente com a sua política ambiental.

Source: ABNT (2004, 2015a).

According to Milazzo et al. (2017), the updated version of the ISO 14001 standard brought a series of significant improvements, outlining a path to superior environmental performance. Among the innovations, proactive actions for environmental improvement, deeper involvement of senior management, detailed product life cycle analysis, improved risk-based thinking, and more effective communication strategies stood out. These changes not only raised the standard of environmental management but also reinforced the organization's commitment to sustainability.

The ABNT NBR ISO 14001:2015 standard did not limit itself to reviewing and expanding pre-existing definitions, such as "documented information", "top management" and "audit", but also introduced crucial concepts such as "life cycle," "environmental condition," "risk," "interested party" and "outsource," while choosing to exclude terms such as "auditor," "document," "environmental target," "internal audit," "preventive action," "procedure" and "document record" (ABNT, 2015a). These changes reflected an evolution in the understanding and approach to environmental management, emphasizing the importance of a holistic and integrated vision.

The standard defined "stakeholders" *broadly* as "a person or organization that can affect, be affected by, or perceive themselves to be affected by a decision or activity," including a variety of examples such as customers, communities, suppliers, regulators, nongovernmental organizations, investors, and employees

(ABNT, 2015a). This definition expands on the importance of considering diverse influences and impacts on business decisions.

The concept of stakeholder, based on classic works in the scientific literature, ranging from the functions of the executive to the nature of cooperation in formal organizations (Banard, 1938), including organizational relations (Andriof & Waddock, 2002), inter-organizational conflict (March & Simon, 1958) and external control of organizations (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978), has evolved significantly. Based on Freeman's (1984) seminal definition, the contemporary interpretation views stakeholders as essential to achieving corporate objectives, a widely accepted perspective in academic and professional business management literature (Donaldson & Preston, 1995).

Organizations operate in increasingly complex and ambiguous environments where stakeholder interactions represent challenges and opportunities (Wu, 2012). This dynamic requires strategic and adaptive management, capable of responding to changes and the expectations of multiple stakeholders.

3 CHARACTERIZATION OF THE BRAZILIAN PLASTIC SECTOR

In its production chain, the Brazilian plastics sector begins with transforming naphtha, derived from petroleum refining, into petrochemical inputs such as ethylene and propylene. These compounds are subsequently polymerized into thermoplastic resins used by the processing industries. Retailers and consumers are at the end of the chain (Bastos, 2009; Moreira et al., 2010; Padilha & Bomtempo, 1999). This sector is marked by an oligopoly in petrochemicals, characterized by a few companies with great market power and significant barriers to entry, in contrast to the plastics processing sector, which presented a more fragmented and heterogeneous structure, with lower barriers to entry and more modest investments (Moreira et al., 2010; Silva et al., 2013).

According to SEBRAE, most companies in the plastics processing sector are classified as micro (approximately 70%) and small (approximately 24%), with a portion operating informally (ABIPLAST, 2014; Silva et al., 2013). This characterization highlights the sector's diversity and complexity, as well as the challenges and opportunities it faces in the context of sustainability and environmental management.

Source: Silva et al. (2013).

Among the production processes of transformed plastics, extrusion and injection stand out as the most used, responsible for approximately 60% and 30% of total production, respectively. Other more common means of transformation consist of blowing, roto molding, thermoforming, and foaming processes, while the recycling of plastic products can occur through mechanical, chemical, and/or thermal processes (ABIPLAST, 2014; SINDIPLAST, 2011).

In addition to resins, manufacturing plastic products requires inputs such as chemical additives, pigments, mineral fillers, elastomers, metal inserts, lubricants, thermal fluids, and lubricants, among others. The equipment used in the various stages of the process is highly powered and consumes a lot of energy. On the other hand, water consumption is saved through closed-circuit circulation systems for heat exchange and cooling of the parts (SINDIPLAST, 2011; Silva et al. 2013).

Regarding the environmental aspects resulting from the transformation of plastics, the prevalence of resource consumption, atmospheric emissions, effluent disposal, and solid waste disposal is observed (SINDIPLAST, 2011). Regarding potential impacts, the case study by Silva, Shibao, and Santos (2014) in the plastics processing industry identified 25 potential impacts, including reducing the availability of natural resources, air pollution, and contamination of soil and surface water.

3.1 Profile of the industry surveyed

Located in the metropolitan region of São Paulo, Alfa has been manufacturing plastic products for the homeware, packaging, and automotive parts markets for almost 60 years. It currently has 720 direct employees and occupies approximately 74% of its installed capacity, which results in the daily

transformation of 65 tons of raw material through blow molding and injection molding processes.

Alpha's environmental management system complies with ABNT NBR ISO 14001:2015 and has a certificate valid until September 2028.

4 METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

This research was designed to deepen the understanding of a complex topic, aiming to generate new knowledge and develop an innovative model to address specific challenges. According to Prodanov and Freitas (2013), such an endeavor can be categorized as exploratory in its objectives, given its search for preliminary *insights* and understandings, and applied in terms of its nature, as it aims at practical and concrete solutions.

The methodology adopted in this study was characterized by a mixed methods approach, balancing the depth and richness of qualitative data with the precision and objectivity of quantitative data. The sequential exploratory strategy, adapted from the work of Creswel (2010), is illustrated in Figure 4, highlighting the Qual/Quan model. This nomenclature indicates that quantitative data complement and enrich the understanding of qualitative findings, thus justifying the initial prioritization of the qualitative exploration of the phenomenon under study (Creswel, 2010; Duarte, 2009).

Regarding technical procedures, the qualitative phase of this research was guided by the action research methodology. This approach promoted a dynamic interaction between researchers and representatives of the organization studied, using various data collection techniques to capture the phenomenon's complexity and multidimensionality (Thiollent, 2007). In addition, the quantitative analysis was performed using the *Analytic Hierarchy Process* (AHP) method, a technique that allows the decomposition of a complex problem into its fundamental components for a more systematic and careful evaluation.

This dual approach, therefore, not only facilitated a holistic understanding of the topic investigated but also provided a solid basis for proposing innovative and effective solutions, aligning to contribute significantly to the area of study and practice.

Figure 4 – Research flowchart

Source: Prepared by the authors.

4.1 Step 1

It consisted of identifying theories and models applicable to the solution of the problem situation by researchers.

4.2 Step 2

It required analyzing procedures, work instructions, and environmental records to select the areas with the most significant links regarding the number of assignments and responsibilities to the Alpha company's EMS and summon the project participants.

4.3 Steps 3 to 8

The focus group meetings compared positions through moderated debates guided by the semi-structured script in Figure 5 below.

At least one member from each department was present for the planned debates. The audio from each session was recorded and transcribed, resulting in a summary table used as a starting point for the next meeting.

According to Krueger and Casey (2000), the focus group principle does not necessarily require voting or consensus. However, it consists primarily of identifying patterns and trends, in this case, identifying the stakeholders in Alpha's environmental performance and their needs.

To determine the requirements to be complied with and met, as recommended by ISO 14001 (ABNT, 2015 p.7), the AHP method adapted for group decision-

making was applied through Individual Aggregation of Judgments [AIJ], in which priorities are obtained through consensus or voting (Dyer & Forman, 1992; Saaty & Peniwati, 2013).

Figure 5 – Focus group moderation instrument

Source: Prepared by the authors

4.4 Steps 9 to 13

The fourth and final meeting was intended to judge the priorities through consensus or a majority vote of the representatives, who initially decided on the weights of the criteria, that is, on the weight of the classes of interested parties and then on the needs or sub-criteria, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Representation of the hierarchy of judgments by the AHP method

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Step 10 involved judging the priority between the types of stakeholders, and Step 11 involved judging the priority between the stakeholders of each type, which are known respectively as weight and relative priorities.

The Saaty Fundamental Scale is used with the following indexes for comparison: 1 for the same importance between the elements; 3 for a moderate difference;

5 for a significant difference; 7 when one of the elements is very strongly more important than another; and 9 to differentiate the extreme importance of one element over another. The values 2, 4, 6, and 8 are considered intermediate between two judgments (Saaty, 1977, 1994).

Stage 12 verified that the consistency ratio [*CR*] reached a value equal to or less than 0.1 (Saaty, 1986, 1987, 1990). Finally, Stage 13 consisted of obtaining the global priorities through the product of the multiplication between the relative priorities of the sub-criteria and the weights of the criteria.

This study used a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to develop a robust environmental management model. Document analysis and applying the *Analytic Hierarchy Process* (AHP) method were instrumental in identifying and prioritizing stakeholders. Focus group meetings provided valuable *insights*, which were subsequently analyzed and synthesized.

5 PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The activities were carried out between May and July 2023. The Purchasing, Legal, Human Resources, Production, and Maintenance departments each designated a single representative who attended all meetings, along with two employees from the Quality department. At the end of all sessions, seven participants were present.

One of the authors acted as a moderator of the focus group meetings and an analyst in the meeting to apply the AHP method. The material evaluated in the document analysis was used to stimulate discussions without controlling the members' participation, as Munaretto, Corrêa, and Cunha (2013) recommended. Applying the AHP method, the researcher transferred the group's opinions to the calculation matrix spreadsheet and treated the data with the objectivity Gomes, Araya, and Carignano (2004) recommended.

5.1 Qualitative Phase

Figure 7 summarizes the results from the statements made in the focus group meetings. Table 7 presents the classification of stakeholders.

It was observed that the identified stakeholders are among the most cited stakeholder categories in the literature (Dragomir, 2013; Fonseca & Domingues, 2018; Freeman, 1984; Shankman, 1999). Although none of the identified stakeholders presented specific characteristics to be classified as dormant, dangerous, or demanding, they were categorized into four main classes: definitive, dependent, dominant, and facultative. This categorization allowed a more detailed and accurate analysis of the priorities and influences of each stakeholder group on the company's environmental performance.

Figure 7 – Mapping stakeholders and their needs

Interested party	Interests		Features	Relevance	Classification
	Focus	Description			
Owners	THE	Improving the environmental performance of production processes.	P _o / L _e / U _r	High	Definitive
	F	Cost reduction with environmental management; brand enhancement.			
Contributors	THE	Protection of human health through improvement of environmental quality.	L _e / U _r	Moderate	Dependent
Clients	THE	Improving the environmental performance of production processes.	P _o / L _e / U _r	High	Definitive
	F	Cost prevention through shared responsibility for violations of environmental legislation, brand protection, and enhancement.			
Financial institutions	F	Refund of financing; protection and enhancement of the brand.	P _o / L _e	Moderate	Dominant
Suppliers	F	Recovery of investments in improvements in environmental performance.	L _{and}	Latent	Optional
Surrounding community	THE	Protecting human health through improving environmental quality	L _e / U _r	Moderate	Dependent
Associations and professional bodies	THE	Protection of human health through improvement of environmental quality.	L _e / U _r	Moderate	Dependent
Industry associations	THE	Representation of the sector before society and public authorities.	L _{and}	Latent	Optional
Government agencies	THE	Regulation of parameters to prevent or mitigate environmental impacts, to protect human health, natural resources, and biodiversity.	P _o / L _e / U _r	High	Definitive
	F	Collection of fees for the maintenance of environmental protection and defense funds.			

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Regarding the classification of the types of interaction presented by stakeholders (Clarkson, 1998; Curzon, 2009), it was noted that 50% correspond to the primary class, that is, those who directly influence the company's decisions and activities, and are represented by owners, employees, customers, suppliers, and government agencies. Financial institutions, industrial associations, associations,

and professional bodies represent 30% of the stakeholders and are part of the secondary class, those who exert indirect influence or participate in the organization's decisions at the invitation of the primary stakeholders. The remaining 20% refer to the surrounding community and local environmental groups, classified as tertiary due to their low power of influence, generally exercised through a primary or secondary stakeholder.

The focus group discussions converged to bring together interested parties according to the similarity of their nature and interests, such as the category of associations and class entities, which involved everything from unions focused on the conditions that affect employees to institutes and nongovernmental organizations that aim for the social well-being of the entire community.

Likewise, the government agencies class brought together representatives from municipal, state, and federal public authorities, such as the Municipal Health Surveillance Coordination (COVISA), the Environmental Technical Agency of the State of São Paulo (CETESB), and the Brazilian Institute of the Environment and Natural Resources (IBAMA).

According to participants, categorizing stakeholders simplified the operations of managing their interests. The organization uses tools to monitor legal requirements and survey aspects and impacts simply by associating them with the identified categories.

However, for Wolfe and Putler (2002), the categorization of stakeholders was reductionist since the heterogeneity present in the groups was not evidenced, nor was the multiplicity of objectives that would characterize stakeholders as belonging to more than one group recognized. According to Sheehan et al. (2005), these limitations and particularities represent the reason for the company to analyze and classify the relationships maintained with its stakeholders and prioritize them in its management.

5.2 Quantitative Phase

At the last meeting, the focus group members acted as decision-makers. They voted on the priority of stakeholders based on the relevance and ranking data obtained in the previous sessions. Initially, the weight of each category (definitive, dependent, dominant, and optional) was judged. Then, the stakeholders within each category were prioritized: i) definitive: owners, customers, and government agencies; ii) dependent: employees, surrounding community, associations, and professional associations; iii) optional: environmental groups and industry associations; and iv) dominant: financial institutions and suppliers.

In general, there was consensus in most of the votes. However, there was divergence among the decision-makers about the importance attributed to the stakeholders of the dependent group. After voting, the priority score was obtained by a majority of five of the seven votes. When consistency was verified,

an RC index equal to 0.151 was found, and it was necessary to reevaluate the judgment.

A new vote was held with a grade of importance unanimously assigned by the decision-makers, and the new RC index achieved was 0.031. For the definitive group, the RC was 0.037. For the optional and dominant groups, there was no need to calculate consistency since, according to Saaty (1977), the calculation of the consistency ratio does not apply when comparisons occur between two elements.

The priorities of each stakeholder were multiplied by the weight of the category to which they belong, obtaining each one's total priority. The hierarchy of priorities is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8 – Hierarchy of stakeholders

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The group of stakeholders that received top priority was 21 times more important than the group that received minimum priority. However, the stakeholders are relegated to lesser importance; in this case, the surrounding community and local environmental groups use the power of government entities to meet their needs (Curzon, 2009).

The absolute priority given to government agencies can be partly justified by the explicit requirement contained in the ISO 14001 standard, which provides for the identification and compliance with legislation applicable to the environmental aspects of the organization (ABNT, 2015a). Another reason would be the company's self-protection against sanctions and fines (Jabbour et al., 2009).

The importance attributed to financial institutions arises from the need for companies to obtain funds for their operations, such as implementing technology and increasing infrastructure, among others. Financial institutions, in turn, have become increasingly rigorous in demanding proof of companies' environmental performance to release funds (Rabelo & Lima, 2009).

Customers influence organizations differently, depending on the economic segment in which they operate. The automobile industry, for example, has

developed its method of meeting its environmental and quality requirements, using internal certification programs and continuous assessments in which poor performance is punished with demerits and progressive fines (Haro, 2001).

The study by Rohati et al. (2016) aimed to investigate the factors influencing the perceived environmental performance of manufacturing companies using ISO 14001 in Malaysia. The study found that environmental policy, environmental training, regulatory stakeholder pressures, and customer pressures were the factors influencing the perceived environmental performance of companies using ISO 14001.

Brisolara, Silva, and Cardoso's (2016) research showed that most companies in the Rio Grande do Sul sought to obtain ISO 14001 certification focusing on market competitiveness; in other words, they focus on the market and not on socio-environmental responsibilities. Such responsibilities ended up being generated as consequences and not as sustainable principles. This does not mean that such actions are not beneficial to society, but rather that they are based on economic principles and not socially responsible ones, as they are sold on the market to society through a green image.

The main benefits reported by stakeholders in this study included the ability to manage environmental aspects more effectively and continuously improve environmental performance; greater compliance with environmental legislation; pollution prevention; a lower level of risk of penalties and litigation; improved stakeholder satisfaction and employee morale; and the potential to access new markets and new business opportunities with environmentally conscious customers. This leads to lower operating costs and new business opportunities, leveraging organizations' competitive position, as in the research conducted by Fonseca and Domingues (2018).

6 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study aimed to present a model that would identify and prioritize stakeholders in the environmental performance of the plastics processing industry as a significant theoretical contribution. To this end, a mixed methods approach was used, and the research was divided into two phases. In the qualitative phase, action research was carried out, which included using the focus group technique to identify stakeholders and their needs and expectations. One of the authors moderated the focus group meetings and followed a semi-structured script, as illustrated in Figure 5. Each session was recorded and transcribed, generating a summary table as a starting point for subsequent meetings. This process allowed the identification of patterns and trends, as recommended by Krueger and Casey (2000).

Next, the *Analytic Hierarchy Process* (AHP) method adapted for group decision-making was applied, using Individual Judgment Aggregation (AIJ). Priorities were obtained through consensus or voting, and the data were treated with the objectivity recommended by Gomes, Araya, and Carignano (2004). The

consistency of the judgments was verified to ensure that the *Consistency Ratio* (CR) reached a value equal to or less than 0.1, as indicated by Saaty (1986, 1987, 1990). This method allowed the hierarchization of stakeholders systematically and judiciously.

Four classes were identified regarding the types of interested parties: definitive, dependent, dominant, and optional, constituting a theoretical contribution. Regarding priority, it was found that the influence of government agencies was given maximum importance.

The research showed the importance of a structured model for planning the Environmental Management System (EMS) in plastics processing companies. Key findings include:

- Improvement of Environmental Performance: The implementation of the proposed model resulted in improvements in the environmental performance of production processes;
- ISO transition strategies: Identified effective strategies for transitioning from ISO 14001:2004 to ISO 14001:2015, highlighting the most valuable requirements and priorities to maximize benefits; and
- Stakeholder classification: The research highlighted the importance of classifying stakeholders into four categories (definitive, dependent, dominant, and facultative) and prioritizing their needs for effective environmental management.

These findings have significant practical implications, providing clear guidance for managers seeking to improve their operations' sustainability and environmental efficiency.

7 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE STUDIES

To deepen and expand the results of this research, it is recommended:

- Alternative Methods: Use the Delphi technique to obtain consensus among experts and content validation to ensure data robustness;
- Replication in Other Sectors: Replicate the study in companies from different economic segments, such as manufacturing, services, and technology, to verify the applicability and adapt the model to different contexts and
- Emerging Technologies: Investigate the role of emerging technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and *Big Data*, in optimizing environmental management processes.

These recommendations aim to validate and expand this study's findings and contribute to the *continued evolution of* environmental management practices across various sectors.

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